

Global isomorphism or rational choice? Problematizing recruitment processes for knowledge workers in an exemplary industry

Refereed Paper

Citation

Arp, Frithjof (2017). Global isomorphism or rational choice? Problematizing recruitment processes for knowledge workers in an exemplary industry. *Academy of International Business (AIB) 2017 Conference*, 3 July 2017, Dubai, UAE. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.581714

Abstract

Organizations depending on globally mobile knowledge workers are assumed to institute suitably international recruitment processes. However, data from 235 advertised positions and 164 recruitment processes in 41 countries suggest they do not. This phenomenon is problematized and, drawing on institutional theory, global isomorphism offered as explanation. Isomorphic recruitment processes that involve contradictions of purpose, formulaic selection criteria and insufficient communication can have far-reaching societal impact: In the higher education industry examined, it may cause insufficiently sound management education that negatively influences the next generation of knowledge workers. Implications are discussed for other industries and a model offered to help integrate theories and provide a basis for further research.

Keywords

International; institutionalism; recruitment; isomorphism, knowledge work; qualitative, problematization